

CAUSATIVITY FROM THE POINT OF VIEW OF THE LINGUOCOGNITIVE ASPECT

Abdulhamidov Sanjarbek Xusniddin o'g'li

English teacher of the department of foreign language in preschool and primary education

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Abstract: The objectives of this study include the selection of prototypical causative constructions of the Buryat language and the means of their representation, the study of the features of the structure and ways of expressing non-prototypical constructions. The definition of prototypical and non-prototypical causative constructions in the Buryat language, of course, should give a new level of study of syntactic constructions. The output of research on the linguocognitive level is necessary for a comprehensive study of the category of causal activity.

Key words: Causativity, linguocognitive direction, linguistics, conceptual categories.

Causativity is also being actively studied within the framework of the linguocognitive direction. Causative constructions play an important role in linguistics not only from a typological point of view, but also represent an area of convergence of linguistics with philosophy and cognitive science. Causativity, being a conceptual category, has a linguistic nature and is a category of a high degree of abstraction. Such categories are of particular importance in the analysis of linguistic phenomena. From the point of view of modern linguistics, it is precisely such conceptual categories as causation that are considered as concepts that are the basis of grammatical categories. As pointed out by N.N. Boldyrev, such categories represent a conceptual association of objects. The concept is formed as a result of human cognitive activity.

The semantics of the verb as a cognitive structure formed by a person in the mind reflects certain ideas about the world. The description of the verb from a modern point of view involves considering the verb as such a part of the lexical material that reflects a certain layer of human existence. The verb is understood in this case as a linguistic form that conveys a certain mental content and has its own verbal and non-verbal representation in the internal lexicon of a person.

Cognitiveness is understood as the property of a language to represent in a generalized form the phenomena of the surrounding reality known to a person and to provide for the needs of verbal and mental activity. Cognitiveness reflects the process of perception and comprehension of reality, which is carried out in a system of concepts typical for a particular language, or in concepts that are a way of reflecting extralinguistic reality and acting as linguistic universals. The term concept, as is known, is central in cognitive science and is defined as an "operational unit of thought", which is part of collective knowledge marked by ethnocultural specifics conscious typified fragments of experience".

The cognitive aspect is of interest to us primarily from the point of view of the prototypical approach, which allows us to answer the question of which construction embodies the content of the concept in the best way. The prototypical link includes cases that fully comply with the definition of the category. The prototypical approach is reflected by E. Rosch in the works devoted to the description of prototypes in categories. This approach is also used by J.

Lakoff, who presents causation as a concept that implements certain prototypical characteristics.

It is known that at first only lexical concepts were singled out and studied, but gradually they began to study grammatically represented concepts Brief Dictionary of Cognitive Terms. Thus, morphologically and syntactically represented concepts are in the focus of the analysis of cognitive science. Morphologically expressed concepts are associated with the categories of morphology, and syntactically represented - with the categories of syntax. A. Vezhbetskaya wrote that "causative constructions show how native speakers of a given language make a distinction between different types of causal relationships, how they perceive and interpret causal connections between ongoing events and people's actions" ..

One of the main questions of cognitive linguistics is the question, "what is the hierarchy of these constructions, namely: which construction embodies the content of the concept in the best way (being prototypical), and which constructions develop this concept in different directions, blurring its boundaries?" . Proceeding from this, cognitive science is dominated by a totemic approach to the study of certain linguistic categories, which allows us to deduce the core and periphery. The core or prototypical link includes cases that fully comply with the definition of the category, and elements that do not meet certain criteria are called non-prototypical. At the same time, the boundaries between the core and the periphery are blurred.

Causativity from the point of view of the prototypical approach is a syntactic concept. Syntactic concepts are an integral part of the semantic space of a language, because a simple set of concepts "without knowledge of the types of relations between them deprives such a space of life and movement". As .D. Popova, a syntactic concept is "typical propositions that have received standard structural schemes in the language system". It is important that the term "Syntactic concept" is used in relation to typical propositions, and "the structural schemes of simple sentences expressing them are in the language system". Such typical schemes are offered as "who has what", "who has what", "who is not where", etc., which express certain concepts.

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